

INTEGRATION OF LOGICAL THINKING AND INTELLECTUAL DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract: This article deals with the relationship between logical thinking and intellectual development of the teacher and issues of its development.

Key words: Logical thought, intellectual development, thinking, skill, pedagogical skill.

Logical thinking and intellectual development are interrelated and complementary processes. Together, they increase the general mental capabilities of a person, develop his abilities to solve problems, receive and process new information, as well as make decisions. Therefore, great attention should be paid to the development of logical thinking in the educational process, because it creates the basis for the intellectual development of students and becoming a successful person.

Logical thinking and intellectual development are complementary processes in the development of human intellectual potential. Their integration expands a person's general knowledge, improves problem-solving skills, and develops creativity. Therefore, it is important to support logical thinking and intellectual development in the educational process, as it builds the skills necessary for students' future success.

Logical thinking is one of the main aspects of human thinking, it plays an important role in analytical ability, understanding cause-and-effect relationships, solving problems, making decisions and systematizing new knowledge. The main feature of logical thinking is the ability of a person to draw logical conclusions and analyze based on various situations and information. This ability is necessary for a person to be successful not only in the process of studying, but also in everyday life, professional activities and social relations.

Through logical thinking, a person organizes his knowledge, learns to use it effectively, and quickly acquires new knowledge. This process is closely related to the intellectual development of a person, because logical thinking helps to expand and deepen intellectual potential. At the same time, intellectual development develops logical thinking skills, that is, as a person's knowledge and experience increase, his logical thinking skills also develop.

Also, logical thinking plays an important role in the educational process, professional activity and personal development. It helps students to effectively

master educational materials, teachers to effectively organize the educational process, to improve the professional skills of specialists and personal development of a person. Different games, exercises, problem-solving tasks and analytical approaches can be used to develop logical thinking.

Logical thinking plays an important role in the mental development of a person and forms the skills and abilities necessary for him to be successful in various fields. Therefore, the development of logical thinking is an important task that should be focused on at all stages of education. This, in turn, is a necessary condition for improving the quality of education and ensuring the future success of students.

Development of logical thinking in a primary school teacher increases the efficiency of the educational process, helps to develop intellectual abilities of students and to form their ability to make independent decisions in complex life situations. This, in turn, creates the basis for an overall improvement in the quality of education and the future success of students.

Logical thinking and intellectual development are two closely related concepts. Logical thinking refers to a person's ability to draw logical conclusions, analyze and make decisions based on certain situations and information. Intellectual development is the process of developing knowledge, skills, abilities and thinking capabilities of a person. These two processes are interdependent, one supports and develops the other.

The role of logical thought in intellectual development

1. Development of analytical skills:

Logical thinking develops a person's ability to analyze problems, determine their causes and consequences. This process is the main aspect of intellectual development, it deepens human skills and helps in acquiring new knowledge.

2. Systematization of knowledge:

With the help of logical thinking, a person organizes his knowledge, brings it into a system and expands it by including new information. This process is important for understanding and using knowledge effectively.

3. Ability to solve problems:

Logical thinking requires the use of different approaches and strategies in solving problems. This ability, in turn, ensures the intellectual development of a person, because through new problems and situations, a person enriches his knowledge and skills.

4. Creativity and innovative thinking:

When logical thinking and intellectual development support each other, human creativity and innovative thinking abilities also develop. These abilities are important in the development of new ideas and effective use of existing knowledge.

5. Reflection and self-assessment:

A person with developed logical thinking has the ability to analyze his actions, decisions and knowledge. This process of reflection is critical to intellectual development because it requires self-evaluation and self-work.

The influence of intellectual development on logical thought

Higher level cognitive skills:

Intellectual development includes the cognitive skills necessary to develop logical thinking. For example, skills such as comprehension, analysis, comparison, and evaluation enhance logical thinking.

Knowledge base:

Through intellectual development, a person's knowledge base expands, which allows further development of logical thinking. The abundance and diversity of knowledge provides the basic information necessary to draw logical conclusions.

Flexibility and adaptability:

Intellectual development develops a person's ability to adapt to new situations. This flexibility plays an important role in logical thinking because it allows us to use different strategies to solve different situations and problems.

Reception and processing of new information:

Intellectual development increases a person's ability to process new information quickly and efficiently. This ability is important in logical thinking because it allows you to quickly draw logical conclusions and solve problems.

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